

HOW ETIOLOGICAL FACTORS AFFECT THE PROGNOSIS OF ISCHEMIC STROKE IN YOUNG PEOPLE

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The thesis

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15425974>

Relevance: The incidence of stroke in young people is increasing. It is often in young patients that the cause of stroke cannot be determined.

The purpose of this study was to study the effect of determining the cause of stroke on the prognosis in young patients.

Research methods: A retrospective study was conducted in Switzerland. The participants were patients who had suffered an acute ischemic stroke at the age of 18-55 years. The cause of the stroke was determined in all patients. The characteristics of patients were studied depending on the presence and absence of a specific cause of stroke.

Results: The study analyzed data from 3,995 patients who had suffered an acute ischemic stroke. The cause of stroke was not determined in 863 (22%) of them.

Patients without an established cause of stroke were more likely to have dyslipidemia (54 vs. 59%; $p=0.007$), were smokers (37 vs. 43%; $p=0.001$), and were more likely to undergo intravenous thrombolysis (27 vs. 31%; $p=0.046$). The risk of recurrent stroke within 3 months was higher in patients with an unknown cause of stroke (adjusted risk ratio 1.72; 95% confidence interval 1.01-2.94).

Conclusion: Thus, in young people, the absence of an established cause of acute ischemic stroke is associated with an increased risk of recurrent stroke.

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